

ISSUES OF DEVELOPMENT OF ECOETHICAL COMPETENCE IN ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION OF THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: The article examines the theoretical basis of improving the didactic support of the modernization of environmental education in the higher education system, the system and effectiveness of the improvement of the modernized didactic support of environmental education. Also, issues of development of ecoethical competence in environmental education of the higher education system were analyzed.

Key words: higher education, ecology, ecological education, ecological education, didactic, modernization, ecotheological, pedagogical, ecoethical, global, systematic analysis, pedagogical experiment, monitoring, adaptation, creative.

INTRODUCTION. In the development of ecoethical competence in students, the issue of combining natural sciences and social and humanitarian sciences on the basis of integrated education is important. It shows two relatively independent processes. First, the possibility of a complex and systematic approach to environmental education arises from the need to harmonize different areas of education, to connect alternative directions based on a single goal. In the second direction, it is necessary to maintain the historical and logical consistency of connections between different forms and levels of ecological education, and to ensure connections between their means and methods. In other words, the common character of these directions is manifested in their relationship to each other. In addition, on the basis of connecting education and upbringing with the interests of nature protection, a general commonality is created, and its features become a necessary condition for the development of environmental moral responsibility.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The issues of modernization of didactic support of environmental education are reflected in the scientific researches of classical period thinkers such as American and Western philosophers I. Kant, G. Hegel, I. G. Fichte, F. Schelling. Also I.L. Vershok, N.A. Sheyafetdinova, Y.A. Shishkina, YE.I. Balakina, E. Khoshimova, E. Karimova, Y. Shodimetov, S. Mamashokirov, E. Usmonov, H. Salomova, D. Rasilev, A. K.

Berdimuratova, S. It was analyzed in the studies of Sanginov, Sh.P. Makhmudov, A. Akhmedov, A. Koldoshev.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In most of the literature, the educational tools for the development of ecoethical competence are explained only as a narrow pedagogical task. However, the problems of the current environmental situation require a broader, socio-philosophical approach to the issue. The tasks of environmentalization of the educational process should consist of the humanization of the educational complex, the interests of harmonizing the relationship between man and nature. That is why the formation of an integrated educational system in higher education, and the formation of ecological and ethical knowledge and skills based on interdisciplinary cooperation activities are gaining relevance.

A necessary condition for the development of ecoethical competence is related to determining the principles of ecological education and upbringing, that is:

1) subjecting human interests to it based on scientific knowledge of the laws of objective development of ecological existence;

2) connecting the practice of nature protection with a concrete environmental situation and ensuring unity of methods and means of increasing students' activity and responsibility;

3) productive, appropriate use of the historical heritage of students' theoretical knowledge and practical skills;

4) to patiently eliminate anti-ecological ideas and even actions in the minds and lifestyles of students;

5) based on the environmental needs and interests of students and young people, wide introduction of new universal progressive norms, customs, and traditions into life;

6) it is necessary to approach the education of environmental responsibility in students in a systematic and comprehensive way, and to ensure its continuity, it is necessary to coordinate educational activities of different levels and directions.

It is methodologically important to distinguish three stages of human influence on ecology based on ecological ethics, namely:

At the first stage, empirical materials and information on indicators of anthropogenic impact on nature are summarized. The material and spiritual heritage of mankind, which is the result of ecological activities, is creatively

studied retrospectively, and practical, theoretical, and methodological special conclusions are drawn from them.

The second stage - from programming and designing the spheres of anthropo-technogenic influence of man on nature according to the law of proportionality of the "nature-society-man" complex, to maintain the ecological balance of the biosphere, to form a system of various environmental control agencies, and at the same time, to create scientific-theoretical and methodological bases of ecological activity consists of

The third stage is characterized by the strengthening of practical activities by creating constructive-rational methods and tools, technical-technological, intellectual bases for the implementation of prospective programs of nature protection, that is, this stage is a new quality level of positive-pragmatic activities. is the "materialization" of ecological theoretical views, their direct transformation into production forces.

The continuous increase in the conflict between the protection of nature and the continuous expansion of material production, on the one hand, goes back to the backwardness of technology, which has arisen as a result of environmental irresponsibility to a certain extent. On the other hand, the reason for not implementing the existing ecological technology as a result of the pursuit of momentary economic profit, putting local, administrative interests above the interests of the people, is environmental immorality and irresponsibility.

The level of awareness of ecological responsibility corresponds to the nature of the historical development of mankind. In fact, in the early stages of socio-economic development, elementary socio-ecological norms, customs related to certain natural living conditions of people, were manifested in practical forms in the form of paintings. To generalize, there are two dialectical trends in relation to environmental responsibility: the first is that environmental responsibility determines the direction of activity in this field, that is, nature conservation activity is a culturalized process of environmental responsibility. The second is that ecological responsibility can become a motive for forming ecological ethics only when it becomes a belief and a daily necessity of a person's practical activity.

Environmental responsibility, which is a component of general social responsibility, is understood in relatively broad and narrow terms. In a broad sense, ecological responsibility is a motive of activity aimed at protecting the natural environment in the process of social-historical practice of mankind. In a narrow sense, it consists in directing the concrete practical and theoretical

activity of people to the protection of nature. Levels of socio-economic development are determined not only in the process of material production, but also by the methods and means by which a person uses nature for his needs. In addition, a person's attitude to the protection of the natural environment shows the characteristics of the society's awareness of social responsibility. Especially in the current era, when the environmental situation is worsening, the criteria showing the level of development of the means of production have gone beyond the scope of purely economic interests.

Without a deep knowledge of the laws of nature, the internal complex connections of the biosphere, without understanding the perspectives of society's impact on nature, it is impossible to determine the necessary practical measures for the protection of nature, the optimal options for the use of nature. In this regard, it is necessary to raise education and training aimed at the formation of environmental responsibility to a new level of quality, to develop theoretical and fundamental research faster than practical requirements.

Until now, the conflicts between nature and society have become so intense that nature has taken revenge on man for his mistakes, and humanity is forced to kneel before nature and repent. High forms of ecological ethical norms, new ethical criteria of attitude to nature are being formed. Purely universal ecological moral norms have risen to the level of politics, the moral content of ecological ideals has led to the wider coverage of other forms of social consciousness.

Implementation of universal ecological ethical norms in practice is the process of materialization of social ecological ethical ideals. The entire set of tasks and perspectives of ecological education is aimed at accelerating this process and morally educating young people for it. In other words, the ethical content and directions of ecological education and promotion should ensure the transformation of ecological ideals into daily practical activities and behavior. Ethical and legal environmental categories such as "Ecological conscience", "Ecological duty", "Ecological responsibility", "Ecological crime" are a reflection of this practical activity and arise from the inevitable laws of spiritual development.

Ecological education consists not only in the formation of theoretical knowledge of nature protection, but also develops practical relations in the relevant direction. The formation of practical environmental activities and the development of skills and becoming the content of a lifestyle is not a simple task that is carried out spontaneously. One of the main tasks of ecological education

is to theoretically justify the conflicts between nature and society in everyday activities of young people, and to direct them to independently find their practical solutions. The central link of ecological education in families and schools is to create awareness of socio-ecological ideals of relations between nature and society in young people. This process is considered to be a criterion of the effectiveness of education in this field only if moral, aesthetic, and legal views become the beliefs and responsibilities of the individual and are manifested in various practical and ecological activities. It is necessary to pay special attention to the ideological features of the formation of environmental activity and responsibility in family and school education.

CONCLUSION. To sum up: firstly, ecological moral responsibility is not a social phenomenon that is formed spontaneously, on the contrary, it is the result of the state's purposeful systematic and collective education policy; secondly, ensuring the continuity of ecoethical education requires a differential approach to its object, taking into account its socio-political, demographic and ethnographic characteristics, and the selection of methods and tools that correspond to the needs and interests of each social group or stratum; thirdly, the effectiveness of ecological responsibility based on high ethical criteria depends on the internal connection of the educational system focused on nature protection, on the use of historical experiences, according to the principles of succession; fourthly, the development of environmental ethics in students depends on the organization of the processes of integration and differentiation of various fields of education in horizontal and vertical directions; fifthly, the necessary principle of the formation of environmental responsibility is to increase the effectiveness of pedagogical and didactic tools that provide the public with objective information about the environmental situation.

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